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The Effect of Cognitive Dissonance on Consumer Purchasing Behavior

ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the factors that influence cognitive dissonance theory on consumer behavior towards purchasing luxury products. According to cognitive dissonance theory, a person will experience dissonance when there is a mismatch between their thoughts, beliefs, emotions, values, and attitudes. This study collected data from luxury product customers in Indonesia to assess the formation of cognitive dissonance in them using quantitative methods with 122 respondents as a sample. The data presented comes from the distribution of online questionnaires which are then analyzed using descriptive statistical methods and linear regression test forms. The research findings interpret that there is a significant influence of cognitive dissonance theory on consumer behavior in purchasing luxury products. The results of this study confirm that when consumers experience a mismatch between their thoughts, beliefs, emotions, values, and attitudes when buying luxury products, they will try to reduce the dissonance. This research provides important implications for luxury product marketers to understand consumer psychological factors, such as cognitive dissonance, and develop marketing strategies that can help increase customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Keywords: *Cognitive Dissonance Theory, Consumer Behavior, Luxury Product Purchases*

INTRODUCTION

Modern human life is dependent on consumption. Consumers are faced with a wide choice of goods, including luxury or expensive goods. When people buy luxury goods, they often experience cognitive dissonance, which is psychological distress caused by beliefs or other negative emotions related to

their circumstances or behavior. The theory of cognitive dissonance (TDC) was coined by Leon Festinger in 1957 and explains that people want to achieve internal consistency in their thoughts and behaviors; when inconsistencies occur, people experience unpleasant cognitive dissonance. Buying expensive items can cause positive dissonance for several reasons, such as social comparison, availability, and price.

The study of consumer behavior is very interesting and complicated because many factors influence people's Purchase Decisions. Cognitive dissonance is a condition in which two cognitive components (beliefs, values, or behaviors) contradict each other, causing a feeling of discomfort. This is a factor that may affect consumer behavior. Consumer behavior can experience cognitive dissonance both before and after buying goods, especially luxury goods.

When people buy luxury goods, the relationship between cognitive dissonance theory and their behavior is critical to their decision-making strategies and post-purchase behavior. There are several factors that potentially have an influence on certain consumer behaviors, such as the conflict between consumers' beliefs and values and their behavior. Marketers and consumers can discover many new things about the cognitive dissonance theory of consumer behavior, especially about luxury purchases, because it can make it easier for them to make better decisions, find more effective marketing strategies, and add value to customer satisfaction and loyalty.

A review of the literature shows that since Leon Festinger (1957) formulated the cognitive dissonance theory, a large number of studies have been conducted and published by older researchers, one of which is O'Neill & Palmer (2004). The researchers looked at how salespeople play a role in causing dissonance among customers and emphasized that companies should ensure that salespeople's behavior and interface generate satisfaction, not dissonance (Jillian C. Sweeney et al., 2000).

In addition, some researchers look at how store aesthetics and music (Jillian C. Sweeney & Wyber, 2002) can help customers feel good about their purchase decisions, which reduces cognitive dissonance (Hunt, 1970). As

customers try to justify their choices, perceptions of service quality change or decrease (George & Edward, 2009; O'Neill & Palmer, 2004).

Cognitive dissonance theory was proposed by Leon Festinger (1957), which explains how people strive to achieve internal consistency in their thoughts, feelings, and behavior. If there is inconsistency, people experience tension and discomfort known as dissonance, which encourages them to do something to reduce it. Cognitive dissonance consists of a person's beliefs, values, and behaviors. According to Festinger, There are three ways to reduce cognitive dissonance:

- Changing one cognitive element: people can change their beliefs, values, or behaviors to match the other elements.
- Obtaining new information that supports an existing cognitive element: people seek information that supports their current beliefs and behaviors.
- Rejecting or ignoring conflicting information: people who ignore information that contradicts what the person believes.

Cognitive dissonance theory is widely used in consumer behavior research. For example:

- Purchasing products that are expensive or that do not match values or beliefs:
- Customers who buy products that are expensive or do not match their values or beliefs may experience cognitive dissonance because they feel they have spent a lot of money.

According to cognitive dissonance theory, a person prefers to think about consequences and does not want to be inconsistent with his thoughts, beliefs, emotions, values, and attitudes. Dissonance consists of psychological imbalance, not logical imbalance, and can trigger a person to act and want a certain impact that can be measured. This research will look at how cognitive dissonance theory affects consumer behavior when buying luxury goods. This research may collect

information about consumer behavior, beliefs, and thoughts about luxury goods from primary and secondary data. Cognitive dissonance theory is also used to measure incongruence.

All the functions mentioned above feel obvious to the customer. When a decision is made, dissonance occurs because before a decision is made, a person has the option to conform to whatever attitude or behavior is considered correct according to his choice. However, once the decision is made, the buyer and consumer have bonded so that they cannot conform anymore and are responsible for following their decision. Consumers may not agree with these commitments and restrictions. The customer feels that all functions are clear.

Dissonance occurs when a decision is made because before a decision is made, a person has the option to conform to whatever attitude or behavior is considered correct according to his choice. However, once the decision is made, buyers and consumers have been bound so that they can no longer conform and are responsible for following their decisions. Clients may not agree with these commitments and restrictions.

This research wants to analyze factors impacting cognitive dissonance theory on consumer behavior through purchasing luxury products. According to the explanation, writer use hypothesis as follows:

- H1: Cognitive dissonance experienced by consumers after purchasing luxury products negatively affects their future Purchase Decisions.
- H2: The emotional dimension of cognitive dissonance negatively affects future Purchase Decisions of luxury products.
- H3: Wisdom of purchase dimension of cognitive dissonance has a positive effect on future purchase decisions of luxury products.
- H4: The Concern over Deal dimension of cognitive dissonance has a negative effect on future Purchase Decisions of luxury products.
- H5: The effect of cognitive dissonance on future Purchase Decisions of luxury products is significantly mediated by its cognitive dimensions (Emotional, Wisdom of Purchase, Concern over Deal).

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

1) Purpose of Study

This study aims to examine the effect of Cognitive Dissonance Theory on consumer behavior before and after purchasing luxury products, and identify factors that strengthen or weaken its influence in making Purchase Decisions.

2) Variable Relationship Type

The type of variable relationship in this study is a causal relationship, namely research that shows the direction of the relationship between the independent variable (independent) and the dependent variable (dependent). In this study, the independent variables are Emotional, Wisdom of Purchase, and Concern over Deal, while the dependent variable is Purchase Decisions.

3) Environment (Setting) and Research Population

The environment (setting) of this research is people in Indonesia who have purchased a luxury product with an online data collection system.

4) Construct Measurement

The measurement of the construct in this study uses a Likert scale, which is a scale that states the category, rank and distance of the measured construct. The Likert scale used is expressed with numbers 1 through 5.

5) Sample

The sample is part of the population consisting of several members selected from the population to be studied (Sekaran, 2006). The sample in this study were people in Indonesia who had bought luxury products as many as 122 people. This number was obtained because it was according to the number of questionnaires distributed and received back by the researcher. Another basis for determining the sample size is Roscoe's opinion in Sekaran (2006), which states that the number of samples > 30 and < 500 in most studies can already represent the population.

6) Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used to select the research sample must be representative of the research population. In this study, the recommended sampling techniques are purposive sampling and snowball sampling.

Data Analysis Method

1) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis is used to see the profile of respondents and how they answer research questions. The results of the descriptive analysis show the data that has been collected and provide results without making overall results.

2) Research Instrument Test

(a) Validity Test

(b) Reliability Test

(c) Multiple Regression Test

(d) Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Test

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1

Frame of Cognitive Dissonance Theory

- a) Cognitive Dissonance: This is the underlying theory in the model. Cognitive dissonance refers to the discrepancy or conflict between consumers' beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors after purchasing a luxury product.
- b) Emotional: This is one of the cognitive dimensions of cognitive dissonance. This dimension measures consumers' negative emotional reactions, such as feelings of discomfort, anxiety, or regret after making a purchase.
- c) Wisdom of Purchase: Another cognitive dimension that measures the extent to which consumers feel confident or doubtful about the wisdom and rationality of the luxury product purchase decisions they have made.
- d) Concern over Deal: A cognitive dimension that measures the extent to which consumers feel worried or dissatisfied with the terms, conditions, or agreements that accompany the purchase of luxury products.
- e) Purchase Decisions: The dependent variable in this model. Cognitive dissonance experienced by consumers after purchasing luxury products is expected to affect their future Purchase Decisions, either directly or through its cognitive dimensions.

In this context, Cognitive Dissonance Theory is used as a theoretical framework to explain how Emotional factors, Wisdom of Purchase, and Concern over Deal influence consumer Purchase Decisions on luxury products through the cognitive dissonance mechanism. This means that cognitive dissonance acts as the main reference in the influence between the dependent and independent variables.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Overview of Respondent Objects

(a) Based on Gender

	Gender	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
1.	Male	32	26,2%
2.	Female	90	73,8%
	Total	122	100%

Table 1

Cumulation of Respondents (Gender)

This table shows that there were more female respondents (90 people) than male respondents (32 people). The percentage of female respondents was 73.8%, while the percentage of male respondents was only 26.2%. This shows that in this study, the sample used was female respondents.

(b) Based on Age

	Age	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
1.	18-20	35	28,7%
2.	21-23	59	48,3%
3.	24-26	10	8,1%
4.	27-29	3	2,5%
5.	30-32	3	2,5%
6.	33-35	5	4%
7.	36-38	0	0%
8.	39-41	2	1,7%
9.	42-44	2	1,7%
10.	45-47	1	0,8%
11.	48-50	2	1,7%
	Total	122	100%

Table 2

Cumulation of Respondents (Age)

This table categorizes respondents by age range. The age range of 21-23 years has the highest frequency, with 59 people or 48.3% of the total respondents. The 18-20 age range is also quite numerous, with 35 respondents or 28.7%. Meanwhile, other age ranges have lower frequencies, ranging from 0-10 people or less than 8.1%. These results indicate that the respondents in this study are mostly young people, especially in the 21-23 year age range.

(c) Based on Employment Type

	Job Type	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
1.	Student	89	73%
2.	Entrepreneur	3	2,5%
3.	Private Employee	27	22,1%
4.	Public Servant	1	0,8%
5.	Tourism	2	1,6%
	Total	122	100%

Table 3

Cumulation of Respondents (Jobs)

The dominance of respondents who are students (73%) indicates that this study focuses on the population or target consumers who are still in the education stage. A significant percentage of Private Employee respondents (22.1%) indicates that the productive age group is also included in this study. The presence of respondents with other occupational backgrounds, albeit in small numbers, provides sample variation that can enrich the analysis. This information can be useful for understanding the preferences and purchasing behavior of luxury products among various occupational groups.

(d) By Type/Category of Luxury product Purchased

Category	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
Fashion	69	56,6%
Accessories	42	34,4%
Skincare	41	33,6%
Cosmetics	32	26,2%
Electronics	62	50,8%
Diamonds	1	0,8%

Table 4

Cumulation of Respondents (Luxury Product Categories)

The dominance of the Fashion category (56.6%) indicates that luxury fashion products are the main focus or main interest of respondents. The high percentage of Electronics category (50.8%) indicates that respondents also have a strong interest in luxury electronic products. The Accessories, Skincare, and Cosmetics categories also received significant attention from respondents, with percentages above 25%. The low percentage of the Diamond category (0.8%) may imply that luxury jewelry products are still less desirable to respondents. This information can provide insight into respondents' preferences and purchasing behavior towards various types of luxury products.

Analysis of Research Instruments

(a) Validity Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.866
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1601.025
	df	153
	Sig.	<.001

Table 5
Signification of Validity Tests

In this study, the KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy (MSA) for the variables Emotional, Purchase Decisions, Concern over Deal, and Wisdom of Purchase (MSA) is 0.866. Because MSA is less than 0.5 and the Barlett test has a significance level of 0.001 and a Chi-square of 1601.025. It can be concluded that the factor analysis test can be carried out. The items on the independent and dependent variables are valid because they have factor loading greater than 0.50.

Only items PD4 and PD5 (statements 17 and 18) are included in the item-by-item questions on the Purchase Decisions variable. The factor loading for these items is less than 0.50, which indicates that these items are invalid. However, when evaluated by means of average validity, this variable already exceeds an acceptable level of validation.

Figure 2

Significations with SMARTPLS

(b) Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.920	18

Table 6

Number of Reliability Statistics

Each variable studied has a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.60, namely 0.920, based on the results of the reliability test, which indicates the validity of each instrument used in this study.

Figure 3

Reliability Statistics with SMARTPLS

- Concern over Deal: Cronbach's Alpha: 0.871. This value is very good, indicating high internal consistency in measuring the "Concern over Deal" construct.
- Emotional: Cronbach's Alpha: 0.925. This value is excellent, indicating high internal consistency.
- Purchase Decisions: Cronbach's Alpha: 0.802. This value is good, indicating moderately high internal consistency.
- Wisdom of Purchase: Cronbach's Alpha: 0.853. This value is very good, indicating high internal consistency.

Overall, all reliability and validity indicators in this table are at good to excellent levels, indicating that the measured constructs have adequate measurement quality.

(c) Multiple Regression Test

		Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.970	.248		3.908	<.001		
	E_RAT	.238	.078	.266	3.050	.003	.592	1.689
	WOP_RAT	.310	.072	.323	4.324	<.001	.806	1.241
	COD_RAT	.226	.074	.265	3.052	.003	.598	1.673

a. Dependent Variable: PD_RAT

Table 7

Collinearity Statistics of All Variable

- Emotional Effect (E_RAT) on Purchase Decisions (PD_RAT)

The regression coefficient value (B) of 0.238 indicates that when the Emotional variable increases by one unit, Purchase Decisions will increase by 0.238 units, assuming other variables remain constant. The standard beta coefficient of 0.266% indicates that the emotional factor has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. The statistical significance of 0.003 ($p < 0.01$) indicates that the effect of Emotions on Purchase Decisions is statistically significant at the 99% confidence level. This result supports Cognitive Dissonance Theory, where consumer emotions (Emotional) play an important role in the process of making Purchase Decisions.

- The effect of Wisdom of Purchase (WOP_RAT) on Purchase Decisions (PD_RAT)

The regression coefficient (B) of 0.310 indicates that when the Purchasing Wisdom variable increases by one unit, Purchase Decisions will increase by 0.310 units, assuming other variables remain constant. The standard beta coefficient value which is in the range of 0.323 indicates that Wisdom of Purchase has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. The statistical significance of 0.001 ($p < 0.01$) means that the effect of Wisdom of Purchase on Purchase Decisions is statistically significant at the 99% confidence level. These result supports Cognitive Dissonance Theory, where consumers' perceptions of the wisdom of purchase have a significant impact on their Purchase Decisions.

- The Effect of Concern over Deal (COD_RAT) on Purchase Decisions (PD_RAT)

The regression coefficient (B) value of 0.226 indicates that when the Concern over Deal variable increases by one unit, Purchase Decisions will increase by 0.226 units, assuming other variables remain constant. The standardized beta (Beta) value of 0.265 indicates that Concern over Deal has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. The statistical significance of 0.003 ($p < 0.01$) indicates that the effect of Concern over Deal on Purchase Decisions is statistically significant at the 99% confidence level. This result supports Cognitive Dissonance Theory, where consumers' Concern over Deal has a significant impact on their Purchase Decisions.

Overall, the results of this regression analysis provide strong empirical support for Cognitive Dissonance Theory in the context of consumer behavior on luxury product purchases. Consumers' emotions, perceived wisdom, and concerns are shown to significantly influence their Purchase Decisions.

Figure 4

Normal P-P plot Regression Display

Based on the Normal P-P plot image of the regression residuals, it can be seen that the observation points tend to follow the diagonal line well. This indicates that the residual normality assumption is met, meaning that the residuals of the regression model are normally distributed. This is one of the important assumptions in regression analysis that should be met. There is no systematic pattern or significant curvature in the plot, indicating that the regression model is well specified and the linearity assumption is also met.

The observation points approach the diagonal line consistently, indicating that the residual variance is homogeneous (homoscedasticity). This is another assumption that should be met in regression analysis. Overall, the P-P Normal plot graph provides strong visual support that the basic assumptions of linear regression are well met. This is a positive indication of the accuracy of the model specification and the validity of the regression analysis results that have been conducted previously.

Figure 5

Scatterplot Variable Dots Display

From the scatterplot presented, it can be seen that the scatter plot displays a fairly wide dispersion pattern of the data, with data points scattered throughout

the plot area. This indicates that there is considerable variance in the data. Despite the wide spread of the data, there appears to be a positive trend between the Regression Standardized Predicted Value and the Regression Standardized Residual. This means that as the predicted value of the model increases, the residual value tends to increase as well. There is no systematic pattern or certain curvature in the data distribution. This indicates that the linearity assumption of the regression model is met. Visually, there is no heteroscedasticity problem, where the variance of the residuals tends to be constant across the various predicted values.

Overall, this scatterplot interprets that the applied regression model has fulfilled the basic assumptions of regression, such as linearity and homoscedasticity. Although there is considerable variance in the data, the pattern of data distribution is still in line with the expectations of a linear regression model.

(d) Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Test

Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Wisdom of Purchase -> Purchase Decisions	0.255	0.253	0.081	3.170	0.002
Concern over Deal -> Purchase Decisions	0.354	0.365	0.099	3.584	0.000
Emotional -> Purchase Decisions	0.320	0.316	0.085	3.777	0.000

Table 8

Path Coefficients Value

Wisdom of Purchase -> Purchase Decisions: The path coefficient is 0.255, indicating a positive influence of Wisdom of Purchase on Purchase Decisions. The standard deviation (STDEV) value of 0.081 indicates a fairly low variability. The T-statistic value, obtained is 3.170, which is more than 1.96, indicating a statistically significant change within the 95% confidence interval. The p-value of less than 0.05 ($p=0.002$) also confirms the significance of the change.

Concern over Deal -> Purchase Decisions: The path coefficient is 0.354, indicating a positive influence of Concern over Deal on Purchase Decisions. The

standard deviation value is low (STDEV=0.099). The very high T-statistic (3.584) and very small p-value (p=0.000) indicate a highly statistically significant effect.

Emotional -> Purchase Decisions: The path coefficient is 0.320, indicating a positive influence of Emotional on Purchase Decisions. The standard deviation value is quite low (STDEV=0.085). The high T-statistic (3.777) and very small p-value (p=0.000) indicate a highly statistically significant effect.

Overall, the results of this SEM test show that Wisdom of Purchase, Concern over Deal, and Emotional have a positive and significant influence on Purchase Decisions. These results are in line and in accordance with the theory as well as the proposed hypothesis, and provide strong empirical evidence regarding the determinants of consumer purchasing behavior.

R Square

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Purchase ...	0.570	0.559

Table 9

R Square Value

In the regression analysis model, the R Square value is 0.570. This means that 57% of the dependent variable in the "Purchase Decisions" variable can be explained or predicted by the independent variables in the model. Finally, the Adjusted R Square value is 0.559. This Adjusted R Square value limits the number of independent variables in the model and the number of samples, resulting in a more accurate estimate of some good models in explaining the variables in the dependent variable. With an Adjusted R Square value of 0.559, it can be concluded that 55.9% of the variables in the "Purchase Decisions" variable can be accurately represented by the combination of independent variables in the model, which also minimizes the complexity of the model and sample size.

In general, a fairly high value is obtained in the R Square and Adjusted R Square values (above 0.50). This indicates that the regression model used has good predictive power, and the independent variables included are able to explain most of the variance in the dependent variable. These results provide strong empirical support for the theoretical model tested.

f Square

	Concern ...	Emotional	Purchase ...	Wisdom ...
Concern over Deal			0.175	
Emotional			0.140	
Purchase Decisions				
Wisdom of Purchase			0.121	

Table 10

f Square Value

In the analysis model, the calculated f Square shows the effect or relative contribution of each independent variable on the dependent variable "Purchase Decisions". Based on these results, it can be seen that:

- Concern over Deal has an f Square value of approximately 0.175. This shows that Concern over Deal has a moderate influence on Purchase Decisions.
- Emotional has an f Square value of 0.140. This means that Emotional also has a medium effect or contribution to Purchase Decisions.
- Wisdom of Purchase has an f Square value of 0.121. This indicates that Wisdom of Purchase has a small-to-medium effect or contribution to Purchase Decisions.

The f Square value ranges from 0 to 1, where: Values below 0.02 are considered small effects. Values between 0.02 - 0.15 are considered medium effects. Values above 0.35 are considered large effects. Thus, the results of this f Square analysis provide insight into how much the relative contribution of each

independent variable in explaining variability in the dependent variable Purchase Decisions. Concern over Deal and Emotional variables have a greater effect than Wisdom of Purchase.

CONCLUSION

Cognitive dissonance theory is proven to have a significant effect on consumer behavior in purchasing luxury products. When consumers experience a mismatch between their thoughts, beliefs, emotions, values and attitudes when buying luxury products, they will try to reduce the dissonance. Marketing strategies that consider the psychological aspects of consumers, such as cognitive dissonance, can help increase customer satisfaction and loyalty in the purchase of luxury products.

For marketers of luxury products, it is necessary to understand the factors that can cause cognitive dissonance in consumers and develop marketing strategies that can help reduce this dissonance. Further research can examine more thoroughly other variables that can affect consumer cognitive responses when buying luxury goods. To obtain more comprehensive results, research can benefit from the use of larger sample sizes and wider geographic coverage.

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